

EPIGENETICS IN PERIODONTAL DISEASE

Abstract

Periodontitis is a chronic inflammatory disease affecting the supporting structures of the teeth. It is a complex disease with multifactorial etiology. Epigenetics provides an understanding of the role of gene-environment interactions on disease phenotype especially in complex multifactorial diseases. The immune response to oral bacteria and the subsequent activation of inflammatory signalling is not only dependent on genetic factors. The epigenetic mechanisms present additional regulatory pathways of genes involved in maintaining chronic inflammation. The term epigenetics relates to changes in gene expression that are not encoded in the DNA sequence itself and include chemical alterations of DNA and its associated proteins. These changes lead to remodelling of the chromatin and subsequent activation or inactivation of a gene. Epigenetic mechanisms have been found to contribute to disease, including cancer and autoimmune or inflammatory diseases. Many Environmental factors such as race, gender, diabetes, smoking etc. can have profound effects on the epigenetic changes. Drugs which specifically target the epigenetic mechanisms may be used as valuable adjuncts to conventional periodontal therapy leading the way to personalized regimes. The understanding of these molecular mechanisms and the early detection of susceptibility may guide in future periodontal disease treatment and prevention.

Keywords: Periodontitis, inflammation, epigenetic mechanisms.

INTRODUCTION

Periodontitis is a complex disease characterized by inflammation and destruction of tooth supporting structures. The definitive mechanism remains unclear, a contributing factor for inflammation and infection is the outgrowth of multiple opportunistic microorganisms in the oral cavity including *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Tannerella forsythia* and *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans* that triggers the host immune response. But the aetiology involves various other extrinsic and intrinsic factors such as genetics and not merely these specific microorganisms that cause the disease. A specific gene possesses different epigenetic patterns depending on the cell type which results as a local and systemic expression of the gene.¹

HISTORY OF EPIGENETICS

Conrad. H. Waddington in 1942 coined the word „Epigenetics“ to bridge genetics, growth, and differentiation. His classical epigenetic landscape explanation on how a cell can attain a different phenotype, led the way to the latest understanding of the epigenetic concept. This has been experimentally demonstrated in *Drosophila* and *Arabidopsis* where heat shock protein 90 (Hsp90) produced different phenotypes.²

In Greek, prefix „epi-“ in epigenetic means „on the top of“ or „in addition to“ genetics. Holliday R in 1994 defined Epigenetics as: The study of the changes in gene expression which occur in organisms with differentiated cells, and the mitotic inheritance of given patterns of gene expression. In Cold Spring Harbor Meeting 2008, Epigenetics was defined as a “stably heritable phenotype resulting from changes in a chromosome without alterations in the DNA sequence”. According to the proceedings at the meeting,

three signaling arms were proposed in epigenetic pathways. Extra cellular signaling initiated by environmental factors referred to as the “Epigenator” that can initiate changes at the level of DNA and non-coding RNAs referred to as the “Epigenetic Initiator” and the “Epigenetic Maintainer” that sustain these changes at the chromatin level to the succeeding generations.³

HOW DO EPIGENETIC MODIFICATIONS OCCUR?

Diet or environmental toxins, exposures to metals, aromatic hydrocarbons (e.g., benzopyrene) found in occupational chemicals, contaminated drinking water, cigarette smoke, fossil fuel emissions and infection predispose to epigenetic changes. Epigenetic modifications turn genes on or off which prevents or allows the gene to make a protein resulting in diseases. Epigenetics is the link between environment and phenotype. Epigenetic modifications include chemical alterations of DNA and associated proteins, leading to remodelling of the chromatin and activation or inactivation of a gene. Epigenetic changes occur more frequently than genetic changes⁴. These changes can lead to the development and maintenance of cancer and autoimmune or inflammatory diseases, including periodontitis. Unlike genetic mutations, epigenetic changes can be reversed. Epigenetic alterations and its associated diseases do not respond to traditional therapies. Drugs that reverse epigenetic modifications are known as EpiDrugs.

EPIGENETIC MECHANISMS

Modifications in gene expression are controlled by mechanisms like

- DNA methylation
- Histone modification
- Non-coding RNAs
- Chromatin remodeling

These are potentially reversible and transient. It can be induced or altered by environmental factors that modulate the gene expression and affect various gene functions. Therefore, it produces a link between the inherited genome and the environment.

DNA METHYLATION

It is a well-characterized epigenetic modification and the most studied epigenetic mechanism in cancer. It plays an important role in numerous biological processes, such as transposable element silencing, genomic imprinting (an epigenetic process that involves DNA methylation and histone methylation in order to achieve mono-allelic gene expression without altering the DNA sequence), X chromosome inactivation, and also in various disease processes including carcinogenesis. It is the covalent transfer of a methyl group from S- adenosyl-L-methionine (SAM) to the 5th carbon atom of the cytosine residue in the Cytosine- phosphodiester-Guanine (CpG) dinucleotides. The methylation process occurs mostly in regions containing a high frequency of CpG dinucleotides, called “CpG islands” in the promoter region of a gene, and is associated with gene silencing in most cases. The process of DNA methylation is catalysed by a family of closely related DNA methyltransferases (DNMT1, DNMT3, and DNMT3b). The methyl groups block the

binding of the transcription factors to DNA. This transcriptional repression leads to “gene silencing.” The exposed methylation sites allow for interaction with methyl-binding proteins, such as methyl-CpG-binding domain proteins (MBDs). Additionally, these proteins are instrumental in assembling histone deacetylases (HDACs) and thus influence chromatin condensation.⁵

HDACs are enzymes which remove the acetyl group from histones. Thus the DNA gets wrapped more tightly around the histones. The closed chromatin configuration leads to gene silencing. Studies in the literature have shown that hypomethylation of DNA is associated with chromosomal instability and activation of transposable elements in human cancers.⁶ Thus, abnormal methylation patterns can lead to the development of diseases. DNA methylation occurs in the cytosine residues of the CpG dinucleotides in the promoter region of the gene.⁷ Hypermethylation of promoter region of genes is associated with transcriptional silencing of gene thereby leading to loss of gene expression. Hypomethylation of promoter region of genes is associated with transcriptional activation of gene thereby leading to gene expression

HISTONE MODIFICATION

Nucleosome is the basic unit of DNA-histone complex in which DNA is associated with octamer of histone core proteins (H1, H2, H3, H4).⁸ Histone proteins can be modified by various post-translational modifications to alter the DNA-histone interaction and change the conformation of chromatin. Most modifications are found in the H3 and H4 histones and these modifications include methylation, acetylation, phosphorylation, ubiquitinylation, sumoylation, citrullination and ADP-ribosylation.⁹

Acetylation of histone proteins contributes to an open chromatin structure and acetylation is mediated by histone acetyl transferases (HATs) and de-acetylation by histone de-acetylases (HDACs). There are two main classes of HDACs, Class I and Class II. Class I includes HDACs 1, 2, 3 and 8, which are found in the nucleus. Class II includes HDACs 4, 5, 7 and 9 that belong to class II a HDACs and HDACs 6 and 10 belonging to class II b HDACs, which are able to shuttle between the nucleus and the cytoplasm.¹⁰ Histone methylation by methyltransferases occurs on all basic residues. Histone H3 methylation is the most studied modification that includes H3 lysine 4 (H3K4), H3K9, H3K27, H3K36, H3K79, and H4K20. H3K4me1 has been shown to have enhancer functions and H3K27me3 is associated with gene repression.

Differential histone methylation has been shown to affect Th1 and Th2 inflammatory responses. For example, interleukin-4 (IL4) and IL17 genes in Th1 cells and interferon gamma (IFNG) gene in Th2 cells were shown to be repressed in the presence of H3K27me3. Histone methylation has also been shown to be important in regulating allogenic inflammatory responses in graft-versus-host-disease (GVHD). Histone H2A and H2B are modified by ubiquitination in cells and play essential roles in stem cell maintenance by controlling pluripotency and differentiation of genes, DNA damage responses, and X-chromosome inactivation. Histone sumoylation is also shown to be associated with transcriptional repression. Sumoylation of H4 suppresses gene expression through recruitment of HDAC and heterochromatin protein 1 (HP1). Histones are phosphorylated in cell cycle regulation in maintaining the physical state of chromatin. Certain growth factors and phorbol ester-activated signaling events result in proto-

oncogene induction with increased phosphorylation of histone H3 serine residues that have been determined to be early gene activation events.¹¹

NON CODING RNA

Non protein coding RNAs (NcRNAs) contribute to epigenetic regulation. NcRNA molecules inhibit gene expression by interactions with the nascent RNA molecule, DNA itself or participating in recruitment of chromatin modifiers. Micro RNA's (mi-RNA) are a group of non-coding RNA's. They regulate gene expression at the post transcriptional level by variety of mechanisms such as direct translational repression, mRNA destabilization or a combination of both.¹² Several mi-RNA's (miR-146a, miR-155 and others) influence T, B cell development and differentiation and play decisive roles in determination of Th phenotypes in several chronic inflammatory and autoimmune disorders such as rheumatoid arthritis and psoriasis.¹³

CHROMATIN REMODELING

Chromatin remodeling refers to changes in chromatin location and structure. This in turn will give rise to loss of tightened chromatin in nucleosome joints to expose cis-acting elements in the gene promoter thereby providing a chance of combination with trans-acting factors.

Bi-directional effect

The epigenetic changes that are induced by persistent inflammation in a given tissue may lead to an exacerbated disease state that in turn may trigger modifications either at the DNA or at the histone level turning off or on key genes. On the other hand, epigenetic changes brought about by environmental factors could create susceptibility and push an infection into a chronic state.

ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

Epigenetic changes are influenced by environmental factors and are reversible unlike genetic changes in DNA. The epigenetic signature is dynamic and changes in response to various environmental stimuli.¹⁴ Disease susceptibility and differences in response to treatment could be contributed to epigenetic modifications caused by diet, smoking, bacteria and inflammation. Epigenetic alterations with inflammation including age related and airway inflammation, bronchial asthma, and autoimmune diseases such as lupus erythematosus and rheumatoid arthritis have been reported. The role of environmental factors has been confirmed by studies done in twin models. Age is considered as a risk factor for epigenetic changes and these changes increases as the age advances. Difference in methylation and histone pattern was demonstrated in 35% of the monozygotic twins in a study done by Fraga et al,2005.¹⁵ As a subject ages, their cumulative exposure to microbial pathogens increases as does their epigenetic modifications such that their periodontal disease susceptibility increases.¹¹ Nutritional factors like vitamin A,D,B12 and folate may cause epigenetic modifications thereby influencing disease progression. Smoking causes long lasting epigenetic changes in the DNA. These are found in current and former smokers. Chronic inflammatory diseases may be due to decrease in histone deacetylase activity /changes in methylation which leads to altered gene expression.¹⁶

ROLE OF EPIGENETICS IN PERIODONTAL DISEASE

Inflammatory response initiates an immune response that involves both innate and adaptive immunity. Epigenetic regulation of gene expression patterns upregulate proinflammatory cytokines and other signalling molecules to activate a full response from immune cells, while simultaneously down regulate anti-inflammatory cytokines. The cytokine genes have been suggested as targets of multiple epigenetic events. Inflammatory signals which activate NF- κ B have shown to alter histone methylation patterns and activate gene expression.¹⁷ Thus, inflammation has some potential to alter chromatin structure via histone structure. Evidences suggest that bacteria play an important role in altering cellular DNA methylation status and environment, aging and stress are involved in epigenetic modification that modify gene expression and disease expression.¹⁸

EVIDENCE FOR THE ROLE OF EPIGENETICS IN PERIODONTAL DISEASE

Epigenetic remodelling events are critical for inducing inflammatory response. Zhang et.al 2010 reported a lower methylation level of CpG sites and an increase in IFN- γ transcription in gingival biopsies of chronic periodontitis sites compared with periodontally healthy controls.¹⁹ Viana et.al 2011 evaluated DNA methylation in IFN- γ , IL-10 in gingival biopsies of periodontitis and non-periodontitis patients .The results showed methylation level of IFN- γ and IL-10 was similar in both groups. Most samples were positive for IFN- γ methylation. Of samples in the periodontitis group, 11% were unmethylated, whereas no unmethylated samples were found for IL-10.²⁰ Stefani et.al 2013 evaluated DNA methylation of IL-6 in gingival biopsies of chronic periodontitis patients and controls, reported that there is no difference in methylation of IL-6.²¹ The progression to periodontitis from gingivitis is characterized by a transition from Th1 to Th2 subsets. During development and differentiation of naïve T cells into various lineages, changes in the chromatin structure occur through epigenetic mechanisms like DNA methylation and histone modification.

Cytokine genes which define the lineage specificity include IFN γ gene for Th1 cell lineage, IL-4 gene for Th2 cell lineage, and IL-17 gene for Th17 cells.²² The expression of one cytokine gene and the permanent silencing of the other are orchestrated using epigenetic mechanisms.²³ Loo et.al 2010 reported a similar proportion of hypermethylation of E- Cadherin and COX-2 expression in chronic periodontitis and breast cancer biopsies compared to non-periodontitis subjects. The epigenetic changes observed in periodontitis subjects are attributed to the irreversible destruction in the tissue.²⁴ Yin and Chung 2011 reported that the presence of bacteria caused epigenetic modifications in gingival epithelia and exposure to different oral bacteria results in differential methylation profile. *P.gingivalis* significantly decreased the tri-methylation of histone H3 K4 protein expression, but *F. nucleatum* did not, which indicates that *P.gingivalis* could suppress the activation of transcription.²⁵

EPIGENETIC CHANGES IN CYTOKINE GENES IN CHRONIC PERIODONTITIS

The cytokine genes have been suggested as targets of multiple epigenetic events. IL-1, IL-2, IL-6, IL8, IL-10, IL-12 gene, TNF α and IFN γ may be regulated by epigenetic mechanisms. TLR-2 and TLR-4, associated with an increased proinflammatory response, are regulated by DNA methylation.

EPIGENETIC BASIS FOR IMMUNE-REGULATION IN PERIODONTITIS PATHOGENESIS

The host immune response is characterized by an innate and adaptive phase. One of the most important immune mechanisms through which the innate and adaptive pathways are interconnected is the TLR pathway. Micro-RNAs have been implicated in controlling TLR responses to the bacteria. A recent study reported that polymicrobial infection with three periodontal pathogens (*P. gingivalis*, *Treponema denticola*, *Tannerella forsythia*) enhanced the levels of the miR-146a in ApoE^{-/-} mice with experimental periodontitis.²⁶ The authors concluded that the elevated levels of miR-146a contributed to endotoxin tolerance by negatively influencing IRAK-1 and TRAF-6 levels at a post transcriptional level and that miR-146a may represent a target for therapeutic intervention in periodontal disease.

The micro RNA expression profile in chronic periodontitis as compared to healthy gingiva was evaluated in a recent study using the microarray technique, and miR-181b, miR-19b, miR-30a, miR-let 7a, and miR-301a expression were shown to be significantly higher in periodontitis group as compared to the healthy group.²⁷ The naïve T cells undergo differentiation into various lineages and during the differentiation process, changes in the chromatin structure occur through epigenetic mechanisms such as histone modification, DNA methylation, generation of DNase I hypersensitive sites.²²

EPIGENETIC DRUGS

Epidrugs are defined as „„drugs that activate or inhibit disease-associated epigenetic proteins for ameliorating, curing, or preventing the disease““. DNA methylation inhibitors (DNMTi) and Histone deacetylase inhibitors (HDACi) are used for the reversal of the epigenetic alterations inside the diseased genome. DNMTi include 5-aza-2-deoxycytidine, zebularine, Procaine, procainamide and MG 98 and HDACi include TrichostatinA, Pyroxamide, Trapoxin A and B and MS 275. Treatment by HDAC inhibitors efficiently suppressed periodontal bone loss in a mouse model of periodontitis.²⁸ Treatment with novel HDAC inhibitors, such as 1179.4b (class I, II HDACi) and MS-275 (class I HDACi), on *P.gingivalis*-inoculated mice resulted in significantly reduced *P.gingivalis* induced bone loss with 1179.4b, whereas MS-275 had no significant effect, indicating that maintenance of acetylation is crucial to preventing bone loss and no influence was found on the level of inflammation. HDACi prevent bone loss and demonstrates that the novel HDACi, 1179.4b reduces alveolar bone loss in an in vivo model of periodontitis.²⁹

Kim et al., 2002 reported on the use of histone deacetylase inhibitor (sodium butyrate) in inducing the differentiation of periodontal ligament fibroblasts into osteoblasts

and concluded that sodium butyrate was a potential therapeutic agent for periodontal regeneration.³⁰ Treatment with 5-aza resulted in an increase in TNF- α mRNA expression in periodontitis patients.²⁰ Combinations of drugs that inhibit DNMTs as well as HDACs may result in synergistic effects

CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE AND PERSONALIZED PERIODONTAL THERAPY

Every person has a unique variation of the human genome. Personalized medicine can be foreseen as a tailored therapy based on the interactions between genetic, clinical and environmental factors affecting that individual. Recent advances in epigenomic approaches allow mapping of the methylation state in the genome, which may help in the identification of epigenetic biomarkers.³¹ Individualized periodontal therapy is the upcoming concept of medical treatment for an enhanced clinical outcome. Genomic approaches are the useful tools that bridge epigenetics and personalized medicine. Patients with epigenetic alterations and associated disorders do not respond to conventional therapy. Therefore, drugs used for personalized medicine can be used to manage these disorders based on an individual's personal genomic profile.

CONCLUSION

Periodontal diseases are multifactorial where genetics and environmental factors interact with each other to determine the susceptibility of the host to inflammation. Epigenetic modifications are responsible for the differential expression of our genetic material. Epigenetic modifications are potentially reversible. Identifying epigenetic patterns associated with the development of periodontitis may also improve individualized approaches that can be used to personalize treatment plans. Individualized and improvised diagnostic tools for earlier detection and ways to halt the disease helps in regeneration and reconstruction of the lost periodontal attachment apparatus with the biology based approaches.

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